

Proposed Augmented Reality (Instagram Filter Try-On) as Promotion Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness for Start-Up Business (Case Study on Small and Medium Enterprise Fashion Brand Boboya Wear)

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ABSTRACT: Boboya Wear is a local fashion brand that specializes in women's fashion that offers daily wear that has unique embroidery accents on each product and has a variety of colors. The main issue of Boboya Wear is bad product sales and tend to be unstable, so that it becomes an issue for Boboya Wear. The purpose of this research is to find out solutions to solve company problems.

One of the problems faced by Boboya Wear is that the product is not relevant to what consumers want or the trend regarding the product has out of trend. Resulting in fluctuating sales and a small variety of products so that consumer choices are low and this caused by bad production timeline and inconsistent promotion strategies. To analyze more deeply the researchers used primary data by distributing questionnaires to analyze consumers and used secondary data from Boboya Wear Instagram and Shopee Insight. Researchers used Ishikawa fishbone diagrams to find out more about the problems faced by Boboya Wear.

After analyzing the internal and external situation of Boboya Wear using 4Ps marketing mix, SWOT, STP, five forces porter, competitor analysis, and customer analysis. The solution is to implement AR Instagram filter try-on as promotion strategy and develop new products and packaging, collaborate with influencers using AR try-on, create bundling promo, and educate the audience about AR try-on technology. The AR try-on technology used is Instagram filter because the installation cost is cheaper and easier. The results of the questionnaire from total 100 respondents agreed that the implementation of AR Try-on could help them in choosing the product they wanted and create shopping experience more pleasant and fun. The business implementation plan that will be carried out is by optimizing the implementation of AR try-on, making new products and packaging and implementing AR try-on.

KEYWORDS: Augmented Reality, Fashion Business, 4Ps Marketing Mix, Porter's Five Force, STP, SWOT Matrix Analysis, Virtual Try-On.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Fashion industry right now can be considered as most competitive industry. Fashion industry involves lot of roles like makeup artist, stylist, textile designer, retail merchandiser, graphic designer, photographer, publicist, and marketing professional. Because of this fashion industry considered as most competitive industry especially during pandemic covid-19 most fashion business going up and down and the completely compete each other.

Trend that changing also contribute fashion industry to be more competitive. Business in fashion industry must continually create a new product based on what trends happening right now. It means a fashion brands need to adapt to new trends and sell more products even there are no guarantee that the products will success on the market. This kind of market that always changing contributes to fashion industry to be really competitive among other industry. In fashion industry brands also need to be creative among other brands. It creates intense competition to create a creative campaign for each product. There is a pressure to create original designs and creative marketing strategy meanwhile lot of competitor probably will replicate the design and strategy easily.

Pandemic situation has certainly shaken some industry like offline retailer as example that had massive declines in sales and traffic at the start of pandemic and now even both have gone to zero. In North America fashion retailers has shut down their doors for customers and workers due compliance with government orders. This announcement caused the brand close the store and having disappointing sales in the fourth quarter of 2019 and declines the traffic in February 2020. Because of this most customers shift the buying behaviour from offline to online. But online retail can't keep pace because customers' engagement with fashion brands is

low and the customers itself tend to stay at home, scrolling through their social media, and the traffic is not converting into sales performance. Even famous retailers with higher online penetration having struggle to pull back customer to spending their money on their products (McKinsey, 2020).

AI investment in the fashion and retail industries worldwide is expected to reach \$7.3 billion by 2022. One of the AI technologies that can increase the efficiency and effectiveness of consumers in online shopping is virtual merchandising. Virtual merchandising allows consumers to buy their products online but still have a pleasant experience when shopping, like being able to see how the product is on the consumer's body.

However, the implementation of virtual try-on technology is not that simple. There were a few challenges of the implementation of virtual try-on technology. Approaching customers using virtual try-on technology can be both advantage and a challenge, the playfulness of the AR experience can enhance customers' sense of connection to the brand, but if it's not embedded in a larger sales ecosystem it does not become a useful tool. Implementation of AR try-on can become one of the retailer's key e-commerce conversion hacks. According to Shopify (2021), conversion rates increase by 250% when products are supported by AR try-on technology. It makes sense because not only customer can choose products freely but customers can take a lot of time to try which product is matched them. By looking to this situation Boboya Wear want to offer simple and colourful fashion products but with implementation of technology to create immersive and pleasant experience when buying Boboya Wear products. Besides of that, Boboya Wear also have a mission to create a simple lifestyle wear that can be used by anyone. The idea of making Boboya Wear is when looking at many basic fashion brands that increasingly popular and phenomenal in Indonesia. One of the brands that inspires us to create Boboya Wear is Uniqlo. Uniqlo inspires us to create a fashion product that can be used for anyone, in any occasion, and the prices is affordable. Until now Boboya Wear still focused on selling woman fashion products with unique embroidery designs but in the future we sure Boboya Wear will be expand to sell men fashion products just like what Uniqlo did.

2.1 BUSINESS ISSUE EXPLORATION

Conceptual frameworks is a presentation that presented written or visually and expected to define relationship between variables. Variables are the characteristics or properties that want to study. Conceptual frameworks basically generated based on a literature review of existing studies and theories. (Swaen, 2015). Conceptual frameworks start by identifying the business issue that has been facing by company. Based on sub chapter 1.3 business issue has been identified, the issue is related of why the sales of the product is fluctuates, the marketing strategy on social media not consistent because the variant of the products is still limited, and most of our customers easily get bored of our products because the variant is still limited. The issue that need to be solved in this research is by creating a promotion strategy to increase the products sales. One strategy researcher wants to implement is by using Instagram filter (virtual try-on technology) to create great engagement with our audience and to increase buying interest of customers.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Frameworks

Figure 2.1 shown the problem that identified for Boboya Wear is fluctuating sales of goods, poor marketing strategy (inconsistent), and less products variant. Fluctuating sales caused by poor marketing strategy so the Boboya Wear products did not match with customer demand, poor marketing strategy caused by less products variant so it was really hard if Boboya Wear only depending on the old product that already out of trends. After exploration of the business problem that consists of fluctuating sales of goods, poor marketing strategy, and less product variant researcher use SWOT, marketing mix 4P (product, price, place, and promotion), and STP (segmentation, targeting, positioning) for our internal analysis. Besides internal analysis, researcher also conduct external analysis by analysing our competitors and consumers, researcher also use Porter Five Forces analysis and external factor like economic growth and fashion forecasting trends.

After conducting internal and external analysis researcher will analyse the root cause of the business issue and how to solve the problem. After researcher finding the root causes researcher want to propose formulate solution to solve the business issue and one of the solution we want to propose is by using augmented Reality (Instagram filter try-on) as promotion strategy by explaining the SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) of using AR as promotion strategy. After we propose the AR (Instagram filter) as a promotion strategy to increase brand awareness so it can solve the problem (fluctuating sales of goods, poor marketing strategy (inconsistent), and less products variant). Researcher will compare the difference between using AR and not using AR as our promotion strategy generally by conducting few information from other brands that use AR as their promotion strategy. If the result after implementing AR technology is better than before implementing AR technology the next step is to focus on improving AR technology on Boboya Wear Instagram as product advantages over competitors. And if the results of implementing AR technology doesn't give any benefit for Boboya Wear researcher will evaluate what kind of strategy that will be useful for our fashion brands because customers behaviour change really fast and Boboya Wear need to adapt really fast too.

2.2 AUGMENTED REALITY

Augmented reality (AR) is the development of a virtual world created through digital visual elements, sounds, or other sensory stimuli delivered through technology (Hayes, 2020). Augmented reality technology is a other version of virtual environment or

commonly called virtual reality. While using virtual reality users can't see the real world around him, therefore virtual reality creates a new virtual object (Azuma, 1997).

2.3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A specific procedures or techniques used to identify, select, process and analyse information about a topic in research paper. The methodology is to critically evaluate a study's overall validity and reliability. Research methodology is a scientific way to obtain data with certain purposes and uses (Sugiyono, 2017).

The research method used by the researcher is a quantitative method by conducting a case study on fashion brand named Boboya Wear. This quantitative research method usually measures objective facts through interrelated research variables. The reason the researcher chooses the quantitative method is that the researcher looks for supporting data for this study using a questionnaire distribution which in the end draws conclusions from the results of the distribution of the questionnaire.

2.4 PRIMARY DATA

The research data of this research will be conducted from two sources; primary data and secondary data. Primary research data will be obtained from audiences who meet the requirements to fill out the questionnaire; namely, woman, have you ever bought clothes online, have bought or never bought a Boboya Wear product, and have used AR Virtual Try-On or at least heard about the technology to answer the questionnaire that the researcher gave.

2.5 SECONDARY DATA

This study has secondary data from textbooks, online journals, articles from the internet, and Boboya Wear reports related from business issue (Instagram Insight and Shopee Seller Insight). Instagram and Shopee insight help us analyse the internal and external business condition. The researcher also added some supporting information from online articles and previous journal research.

2.6 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design defines the strategies that researchers use to integrate or combine the various components of research in a coherent and logical way (D.A, 2006). The function of research design is to ensure that the evidence obtain when doing research is effectively solve the research problem and unambiguously (Creswell, 2018). The collection, measurement, and analysis of data from a blueprint can be defined as a research design (D.A, 2006).

2.7 ROOT CAUSE ANALYSIS

Root cause analysis is a tool or method that helps researchers to find out the root cause of a business problem and find out what is the best solution for the problem. Root cause analysis help business to solve the problem by creating efficient corrections to prevent similar problems in the future. Diagram that we used for identifying the problem is using Ishikawa fishbone diagram.

Figure 2.2 Ishikawa Fishbone Diagram

3.1 ANALYSIS OF BUSINESS SITUATION (INTERNAL)

For now, the problem faced by Boboya Wear is the lack of customer buying interest in Boboya Wear products, when launching the first product on March 2021, consumer enthusiasm is very high and product turnover moves quickly for new brands. And now, in our opinion, consumer behaviour is changing, which may be caused by a small variety of products, the content presented on social media is too hard-selling, the lack of interaction between consumers and brands. In case of that Boboya Wear will analyse internal condition by using STP (segmenting, targeting, and positioning) and Marketing Mix 4P (product, price, place, promotion) Using STP method is to know how is the segmented audience of Boboya Wear, how is the targeting of Boboya Wear audience, and how Boboya Wear positioning the brand itself on the market so Boboya Wear can penetrate the market among competitors. Using Marketing Mix 4P method is to know how Boboya Wear product compete with competitors, how is Boboya Wear products price compare with other fashion brands, where is the place of Boboya Wear sell the products, and how Boboya Wear promote the products and make customers interest buying the products.

3.1.1 Segmentation

Table 3.1 STP of Boboya Wear

Segmentation		
Geographic	Demographic	Psychographic
Region: Greater Jakarta, West Java, Central Java, and East Java	Age: 15-30 years old Gender: Woman Occupation: High school student, college student, employee	Social class: Middle-up income Lifestyle: love to hang out with friends, love to online shopping, looking for affordable simple fashion products.

3.1.2 Targeting

After describing Boboya Wear segmenting, the targeting stage of STP refers to which consumers target we want to target. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2008) the target market is a group of consumers who have the same characteristics or needs and this target market can be used by the company for promotion. There were many customers that can be targeted by Boboya Wear because for this situation Boboya Wear can't serve customers from all regions because the product variants are still limited and Boboya Wear is afraid can't meet the demand if targeting all regions in Indonesia. The target market of Boboya Wear is women who like unique, cute, colourful, and comfortable lifestyle products to accompany them. Boboya Wear also target customer who lives in big cities in Indonesia like Jakarta, Bandung, Yogyakarta, Surabaya, and others.

3.1.3 Positioning

After describing Boboya Wear market target, the next step is how we explain the position of our products in the market. Positioning is how the company can provide the image, perception, and imagination of the products offered to consumers through communication and positioning the products how we make the products is different with competitors and what makes it better. Positioning is a way for a company to create a perception of a product, brand, or even the company itself when compared to competitors products, brands, or companies by customers (Tjiptono and Chandra, 2012).

The products offered by Boboya Wear is a simple, colourful, and comfortable lifestyle product for accompany daily activities like hang out with friends, go to school or college, and go to work. Our products is made for customers who don't want to bother in the mix and match clothes because Boboya Wear products have colourful colours but are easy to combine colours and can be used in all situations, both formal and non-formal.

3.2 MARKETING MIX 4P

Marketing mix 4P is marketing model to enhance the way companies promote a new products or services to market. Marketing mix 4P help companies to define marketing option in term of product, price, place, and promotion so the product or services that companies offer will meet what customer need. Boboya Wear offer minimalist fashion products to accompany daily activities. Boboya Wear aim comfortable and colourful lifestyle products for its customers. Price element also really important especially when we offering products offline or online, before we put price of products, we will analyse the competitor first and compare the price with competitor before sell the products into the market. Boboya Wear offers a fashion products variant with an affordable price, it starts from IDR 110,000-139,000.

Boboya Wear sells its products online in Bekasi and the average buyer is domiciled in Jakarta, West Java, Central Java, and East Java. The location factor is also very important because if the seller is far from the potential buyers/customers the shipping costs from the seller to the buyer will be expensive and make the buyer rethink to buy the products because the shipping costs are expensive. Boboya Wear has made several promotions through Instagram by optimizing Instagram ads to reach potential customers and make them interested buying Boboya Wear products. One of the useful promotions through Instagram is by set up products give away. This promotion strategy help increase Boboya Wear followers and engagement. Boboya Wear also try paid influencer to promote the products but unfortunately the results are not as we expected, probably because the products doesn't fit with influencer audience.

3.3 ANALYSIS OF BUSINESS SITUATION (EXTERNAL)

External analysis is conducted to analyse external factor influence the company. Most company can't control the external factor but company can create strategy to anticipate the worst possible thing that will happen to the company. External analysis that author use is five forces porter, competitor analysis, customer analysis, and external factor like economic growth and forecasting trends. External business analysis is important to assess whether the current business can be developed more broadly or not. One of the tools or methods researchers used to analyze the business externally is using the five forces porter, competitor analysis, consumer analysis, and a few supporting information based on previous articles or journal research.

3.3.1 Five Porter

Model that designed to identifies and analyse five competitive forces that shape every industry and helps determine industry weakness and strengths is called Five Force Porter. Five forces porter can be applied on many industries to find out the weakness

and strengths of the companies. Five forces porter used to understand the level of competition of companies in certain industry and how to enhance the long-term profitability (The Investopedia Team, 2020).

Competitive rivalry in fashion industry considered as high because fashion industry are basic human needs and there are lot of new comer fashion brand that join the marketplaces. Fashion industry also easy to running besides other business industries and moreover here in Indonesia there are lot of vendor can help many brands realize their idea into products. Minimalist and simple life wear fashion has been part of lifestyle right now, brands like Muji or Uniqlo considered as a pioneer of minimalist and simple life wear. Boboya Wear join into the markets a new comer that offer a minimalist and simple life wear with affordable prices and good products quality. The power of suppliers also affect the brands to produce a new products, because when the material of the products that brought from supplier increase high it will affect to Boboya Wear production costs. It makes the bargaining power of suppliers become high because sometimes the price increase but sometimes the price is stable.

To handle the bargaining power of buyer in fashion industry is to create a product differentiation among others. Boboya Wear has been create a added value on the products like always give free sticker, pin, warranty card, and premium packaging. Besides of that the model of Boboya Wear products also catchy and can be wear in any occasion. To prevent the bargaining power of buyer for Boboya Wear is by always give good offer to Boboya Wear customers like giveaway products, create a special discount, and other. The threat of new entrants can be dangerous for Boboya Wear because lot of people can easily create a fashion brand by producing it massively. But Boboya Wear here offer a different product that give a simplicity of lifestyle wear with affordable prices. Boboya Wear also give added value that researcher already mentioned on previous paragraph (free sticker, pin, warranty card, and premium packaging).

So, Boboya doesn't need to worry of new entrant can affect the business as long Boboya Wear always produces something new and related with what customers want. Threat of substitute products considered low for Boboya Wear because if there are many fashion products like outerwear, vest, t-shirt, shirt, blazer, and others there are low chance to replace the fashion products by other products. But in my opinion, fashion substitution products can be replaced with eco-friendly fashion products and researcher also think that consumers not yet adapted to eco-friendly fashion products.

3.3.2 Competitor Analysis

Competitor defined as a person, team or company that competing each other and it can be in form of produce or services that identical by adjusting the pricing point (Cambridge Dictionary, 2022). . The benefit of competitor analysis is to help build better strategies to compete competitor dominate them. In this research there are two competitors named Shopatkey and Dizayn. Both brands are used to selling similar products and also bring the same concept of "comfortable and simple lifestyle wear".

Table Price Comparison

Products	Current Price	Dizayn Price	Shopatkey Price	Best Price
Vest	110.000-125.000	110.000	175.000	129.000
Outerwear	139.000	129.000	160.000	139.000

3.3.3 Customer Analysis

Customer defined as a individual or business that purchase a products or services from another company (Kenton, 2021). The most important thing when running a business is a customer because customers drive revenues, without customer business won't exist. Customer analysis is a critical component of any business in all stages of growth and when we conducting customer analysis is to define who is the target market and create a strategy how to reach them effectively (CMG consulting, 2021). Customer analysis is done to find out how customers will give feedback to the products offered and to see how customer behaviour and perception of Boboya Wear product. Customer analysis is done to find out if there is any feedback from customers about Boboya Wear products so we can evaluate the products and create better products in the future.

3.4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Respondent in this study are consumers who bought fashion product online, already buy the Boboya Wear product or not yet buy the product, and at least ever heard of AR Virtual Try-on technology or have used the technology. This research is aimed to find out

how customers will react of usefulness, playfulness, enjoyment of using AR Virtual Try-on technology and does it increase the buying interest when buying fashion products if the brands have AR Virtual Try-on features.

Figure 3.1 General Characteristics

Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On technology makes the shopping experience more comfortable and enjoyable

Figure 3.2 Perceived Playfulness on Comfortable and Enjoyable

Based on figure 3.2, 49 out of 100 of the respondents is strongly agree that AR Virtual Try-On technology create immersive shopping experience. 47 out of 100 the respondent is agree that AR Virtual Try-On technology can make the shopping experience become more immersive and fun. 4 out of 100 respondent is tend to be neutral towards use AR Virtual Try-on technology. It shows that AR Virtual Try-On can give fun shopping experience and more comfortable.

Online shopping for fashion products using Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On technology makes it easier for me to make product purchasing decisions

Figure 3.2 Perceived Playfulness on Product Purchasing Decisions

Figure 3.2 shows 43 out of 100 respondents is strongly agree that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help consumers in making purchasing decisions. 47 out of 100 respondents is agree that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help consumers in making purchasing decisions. 3 out of 100 is tend to be neutral toward use of AR Virtual Try-On technology. 7 out of 100 respondents is disagree and strongly disagree that utilization of AR Virtual Try-On technology can help customers decides buying the products.

Using Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On technology can increase efficiency and effectiveness in shopping for fashion products online.

Figure 3.3 Perceived Usefulness on Efficiency and Effectiveness

Figure 3.3 shows 45 out of 100 respondent is strongly agree that AR Virtual Try-On technology can increase efficiency and effectiveness when buy fashion products by online. 46 out of 100 respondent is agree that AR Virtual Try-On technology also can increase the efficiency and effectiveness when buy fashion products by online. And 6 out of 100 respondent is tend to be neutral of useful of AR Virtual Try-On technology. 3 respondent is disagree that AR Virtual Try-On can increase efficiency and effectiveness when buy fashion products online. Based on figure 3.3 it shows that AR Virtual Try-On can increase efficiency and effectiveness when customer want to buy fashion products online because AR Virtual Try-On can help them to see the overview of the product virtually.

Using Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On technology in shopping for fashion products online can increase the suitability of the product according to the style I want.

Figure 3.4 Perceived Usefulness on Product Match

Figure 3.4 shows 50 out of 100 respondent is strongly agree that the useful of AR Virtual Try-On technology when buying fashion product online is can increase the suitability of the product with customers desired style. 49 out of 100 respondent also agree too that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help increase the suitability of the products with desired style. 3 out of 100 respondent is tend to be neutral of useful the AR Virtual Try-On technology. And the rest of the respondent is strongly disagree that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help customers get the desired style.

Using Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On technology in shopping for fashion products online can help me choose the color of the clothes I want.

Figure 3.5 Perceived Usefulness on Product Color

Figure 3.5 shows that 47 out of 100 respondents strongly agrees that the usefulness of AR Virtual Try-On technology when buying fashion products online can help customers choose product colour that is suitable for customers. 43 out of 100 respondents is agreed too that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help customers choose products colour that suitable for them. 8 out of 100 respondents tends to be neutral, and the rest of the respondent is disagreed that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help customers choose what products colour. But brands need to create a lot of varieties in order to maximize the usability of the AR Virtual Try-On technology.

I think it would be nice to use Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On technology to provide a diverse product overview

Figure 3.6 Perceived Enjoyment on Product Overview

Figure 3.6 shows that 49 out of 100 respondent is strongly agrees that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help give product overview with immersive and fun experiences. 50 out of 100 respondent also agrees that AR Virtual Try-On can help give product overview with immersive and fun experiences too. 1 out of 100 respondent tend to be neutral either they are disagree or agree. It shows on the following figure that AR Virtual Try-On can help customers give a product overview virtually on customers bodies and it will be really fun for customers.

I think using Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On technology to try different types of fashion products will provide a pleasant experience.

Figure 3.7 Perceived Enjoyment on Shopping Experience

Figure 3.7 shows that 46 out of 100 respondent strongly agrees that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help try a lot of fashion products without having a commitment to buy the products and it gives fun experiences. 52 out of 100 respondents is agreed too that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help customers try a lot of products virtually and gives fun experiences. 2 out of 100 respondents tend to be neutral answering the questionnaire. It also shows on the following figure the usability of AR Virtual Try-On can help customers try lot of product varieties without having commitment to buy the products. It also gives immersive and fun shopping experiences.

I think the use of Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On technology is interesting because it can provide a virtual picture of fashion products

Figure 3.8 Perceived Enjoyment on Virtually Product Overview

Figure 3.8 shows that 51 out of 100 respondent strongly agrees that AR Virtual Try-On can provide fashion products virtually. 48 out of 100 respondents is agrees that AR Virtual Try-On technology can help give fashion products an overview virtually. 1 out of 100 respondents tend to be neutral either they disagree or agree. It shows on the following figure that AR Virtual Try-On is interesting because customers can get the product overview on their bodies virtually.

Fashion brands that have the Augmented Reality Virtual Try-On feature can increase my buying interest before purchasing the product

Figure 3.9 Buying Interest on Fashion Brand That Have AR Try-On

Figure 3.9 shows that fashion brand that have AR Virtual Try-On technology can increase customers buying interest with 42 out of 100 respondent strongly agreed. 49 out of 109 respondent agrees that AR Virtual Try-On technology can increase customers buying interest. 7 out of 100 respondent is tend to be neutral. And the rest of the respondent is disagree that AR Virtual Try-On technology can increase customers buying interest.

Figure 3.10 Buying Interest on Fashion Brand That Have AR Try-On

Figure 3.10 shows that 18 out of 108 respondents is strongly agreed that customers will buy fashion products that have AR Virtual Try-On technology. 37 out of 100 respondents also agreed that customers will buy fashion products that have AR Virtual Try-On technology. 28 out of 100 respondents tend to be neutral and the rest of the respondents is disagreed and strongly disagree. It seems that if the brands have the AR Virtual Try-On technology it would be a great added value and even if the brand doesn't have the technology, that's not a big issue.

Figure 3.11 Buying Interest on Fashion Brand That Have AR Try-On

Figure 3.11 shows that 18 out of 108 respondents are strongly agreed will find fashion brands that have AR Virtual Try-On technology before buying the products. 38 out of 100 respondents is agreed will find fashion brands that have AR Virtual Try-On technology before buying the products. 21 out of 100 tends to be neutral. The rest of the respondents is disagreed and strongly disagree that they will buy fashion products from a fashion brands that offers AR Virtual Try-On technology on their products. According to all following figure from perceived playfulness, perceived usefulness, perceived enjoyment, and buying interest it shows that most of the respondent is strongly agree and agree that AR Virtual Try-On features can create immersive and fun shopping experience because customers can see the product overview on their bodies virtually. It also shows that by implementing AR Virtual Try-On can help them decide to buy the fashion products and can increase efficiency and effectiveness of online shopping experiences. Most of the respondent agree that AR Virtual Try-On can increase buying interest but respondent doesn't really care if the fashion brands doesn't have the AR Virtual Try-On technology. But if the brand offers the features it will be good advantages point for the brands.

3.5 SWOT ANALYSIS

SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) is a analysis framework that used to evaluate company competitive position in current industry and to propose or develop new strategic planning to compete with other competitors (Kenton, 2021). The overall evaluation of company strengths, weakness, opportunities, and threats it's called SWOT analysis by monitoring the

internal and external factor (Kotler and Keller, 2016). SWOT analysis consist of four elements there were strengths that explained the strengths of the company among competitor, weakness that explained the weakness of the company, opportunities that explained the opportunities that company had among other competitor, and threats explained the threat that will bring obstacle to company.

Table 3.2 SWOT Analysis of Boboya Wear and Instagram Filter Try-On

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Affordable Prices. High quality production and materials of each products. Product comes up with good packaging and bonus inside the package. (Water Resistant package use poly mailer) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Product variants is still limited. (Each release there are only four variation with 2-3 dozen each variation) Production timeline still often miss schedule. Marketing strategy of Boboya Wear still inconsistent and not well prepared. No physical store.
Opportunities	Threats
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Have big opportunity to penetrate the market using marketplace as platform. Social media growth really fast year by year (Tiktok and Instagram). Capture the young generation customers. Make some collaboration with influencer or brands to penetrate the market and increase brand awareness and brand value. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> There are too many competitor in fashion industry and big competitor always comes up with very low price products with lot of varieties. Dependent to the third-party production (convection). Rising competition in marketplace.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Can visualize the product on the consumer's body easily. Directly integrated with Boboya Wear Instagram followers and can be used directly by followers Cheaper cost compared to using the website as a virtual try-on platform. Can increase brand awareness and reduce return rates. Installed permanently on Boboya Wear Instagram without charge any costs after installation. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Need to educate the audience about using Instagram try-on filters. It doesn't directly affect sales, but there must be several steps first, by educating and increasing Boboya Wear Instagram traffic first.
Opportunities	Threats
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Potentially increase sales, brand image, brand value, and brand awareness of Boboya Wear. Increase consumer buying interest in Boboya Wear products because of a pleasant shopping experience. Can visualize all Boboya Wear products with Instagram filters try-on at a low cost. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> There is a barrier to entry for Boboya Wear followers who may not be tech-savvy

4.1 CONCLUSION

1. Boboya Wear must be able to quickly adapt to new trend. According to McKinsey report Boboya Wear has to learn more data-driven product development by adjusting their consumers new lifestyles. Brands can't continue to rely on their highest income products, but must continue to innovate, issue the latest and follow trends. This is a challenge for Boboya Wear to continue to adapt to existing trends or create their own trends.
2. AR that can be implemented by Boboya Wear is Instagram filter virtual try-on to solve the current business issue. The advantages of using AR Instagram filter try-on is to reduce return rate, according to McKinsey report purchasing clothes using AR helps customers to minimize expensive return rate. And other benefit of using AR Virtual Try-On is customers can improve personalization based on customers preferences, and there is no contact try-on so it will be more safe for customers.
3. To optimize the usability of Instagram Filter Try-On Boboya Wear need to develop new product and implement the AR Try-On features, new packaging, new sample simultaneously with AR Instagram Try-On. Other than that Boboya Wear need to create physical store and own production house, online websites, and optimize the marketplace platform. Boboya Wear need to determine new prices with special discount if customers use Boboya Wear AR Instagram Try-On and share it on their Instagram stories, bundling product of old stock
4. Boboya Wear need to consistently upload a content on Instagram and Tikok, collaborate with influencers and promote the products using Boboya Wear AR Instagram filter try-on, and optimize the usability of AR Instagram filter try-on by give discount for those upload their experience using Boboya Wear Instagram filter try-on.

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Cite this Article: Dimas Kamil Prayogio (2022). Proposed Augmented Reality (Instagram Filter Try-On) as Promotion Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness for Start-Up Business (Case Study on Small and Medium Enterprise Fashion Brand Boboya Wear). International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(6), 2089-2103